

Triangle of Inequalities: Gender, Research Funding and Open Access in Spain

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Abstract

Gender inequalities in science are widely documented, yet their persistence is often examined through isolated dimensions such as productivity, funding or publishing practices. This study provides an integrated analysis of how funding patterns, team structures and Open Access practices are associated with women's participation in scientific production in Spain. Using large-scale bibliometric data from Web of Science (2008–2017), we analyse publications with at least one Spanish author, combining information on author gender, funding acknowledgements, authorship roles and Open Access status across five broad scientific fields.

The results reveal that gender inequalities are not driven by a single mechanism, but emerge from the interaction of structural factors. Women are underrepresented in internationally funded publications and in senior authorship positions, while they appear more frequently as first authors. Mixed-gender teams consistently show more balanced participation and higher productivity for women, highlighting collaboration as a key equalising context. Open Access uptake is shaped by funding availability rather than gender, and incomplete funding information remains a major obstacle for monitoring equity and visibility.

This study is particularly timely in the context of ongoing reforms in research assessment. By offering integrated, system-level evidence, it contributes to debates on responsible metrics, funding transparency and inclusive assessment practices. Rather than proposing new evaluative criteria, the findings provide diagnostic insights to support evidence-informed reforms aimed at reducing structural gender inequalities in science.

Keywords: Gender inequality, Research funding, Authorship roles, Open Access, Responsible metrics, Spain.

Introduction

In recent decades, research on women's¹ situation in science has grown substantially, reflecting persistent structural inequalities across education, research careers, and institutional environments (González-Salmón et al., 2025). Advances in bibliometric methods have enabled more comprehensive analyses of these inequalities, allowing researchers to disentangle gendered patterns in scholarly communication, evaluation, and recognition (Larivière et al., 2013). Although findings vary significantly across disciplines, countries, and time frames, the literature consistently shows that, despite notable improvements, the academic ecosystem still falls short of ensuring equal treatment and opportunities for all genders (Huang et al., 2020). Given ongoing transformations in research assessment and the widespread adoption of responsible metrics principles (e.g. CoARA, DORA) further examination of these issues is especially timely.

Bibliometric studies have examined gender differences in multiple dimensions of scientific activity, including authorship (e.g., Demaine, 2021), relevant roles in the byline of publications (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2025), citations (Wu, 2024), presence at conferences (e.g., Santosa et al., 2019), collaborations patterns (Morillo et al., 2025), and contributions (e.g., Macaluso et al., 2016), among many other topics. While some areas have received more attention than others, the study of gender bias in research funding presents a particularly paradoxical case: it has been extensively researched, yet no clear consensus has emerged regarding the extent to which women face

¹ Throughout this article, we use women/men to refer to gender rather than female/male.

disadvantages in this domain (Cruz-Castro et al., 2022). This lack of clarity may be attributed to the complexities of funding systems, both in terms of methodological challenges in data cleaning and privacy restrictions that limit data accessibility. Another underexplored area is the relationship between gender and Open Access (OA) publishing. OA is a comparatively recent topic in scientometric studies that only began to examine gendered dimensions (Zhu, 2017; Olejniczak and Wilson, 2020).

Understanding gender dynamics in funding is key as biases in obtaining research funds to develop research can shorten women's careers, reduce recognition, and limit collaborations opportunities, reinforcing cumulative women's disadvantages over time that perpetuate and privilege men's practices and norms (Aiston and Jung, 2015). At the same time, OA practices have become a central characteristic of the present and future of scholarly communication (Ma et al., 2023), and examining its gendered implications is essential for informing equitable science policy frameworks (Chtena et al., 2025; Barreiro-Gen and Bautista-Puig, 2022; Gender Action, 2018).

In this regard, there is a pressing need to understand how these elements interact, and not much research has explored this relationship. One notable exception is Ruggieri et al. (2021), who explored the intersection of gender, funding, and OA practices in Italy (2016-2018), and found that women are more inclined than men to publish OA and highlight the importance of discipline-specific practices. However, evidence remains fragmented, and the combined analysis of gender, funding, OA practices, and authorship roles is still largely unexplored.

This research seeks to contribute to this emerging field by analyzing the relationship between gender, research funding, and OA publishing in Spain. Our aim is twofold, with two main research questions driving the research:

RQ1: How are research funding and OA practices distributed across genders and disciplines?

RQ2: What roles do women occupy within research teams, and how are these roles associated with funding patterns and OA publishing?

To address these questions, we draw on Web of Science data (2008–2017), which constitutes the primary source used by national agencies for researcher accreditation in Spain. We argue that examining the interplay between gender, funding, Open Access and relevant team roles can open up policy-relevant lines of inquiry regarding equity and visibility in science.

Literature Review

Building on this perspective, we structure the literature review by examining how gender intersects with each of these three dimensions: funding allocation, Open Access practices and authorship positions. We conclude the section by reflecting on the potential interdependence of these variables and how their combined analysis may contribute to a more nuanced understanding of gendered dynamics in scientific production.

Gender and funding

Bibliometric methods have allowed us to study and gain a deeper understanding of the inner dynamics of funding in science. Research has been done at different levels. At the macro-level, studies have focused extensively on the relationship between funding and outputs in different countries (i.e., Man et al., 2004; Leydesdorff and Wagner, 2009; Wang et al., 2012). More recently, scholars have used funding data to reveal dependencies within international science (Miao et al.

2024), identify success factors (Aagaard and Schneider, 2016), and shed light on challenges faced by developing economies (Sanganyado, 2021).

At the micro-level, that is, the individual researcher level, literature draws on funding as a determinant of individual careers and disciplinary trajectories. Studies have explored funding differences across career stages (Bol et al., 2018) and disciplines (Wu, 2015). A significant body of research has also investigated gender differences in funding success. Studies have found that women rely more on national than international funding (Ruggieri et al., 2021), that a ‘motherhood penalty’ can affect access to funding (Lawson et al., 2021), and that there is a ‘halo effect’ whereby men’s work is evaluated more favourably (Liao and Lian, 2024). In this context, studies denounce the loss of women talent due to a sexist allocation of funding (Boivin et al., 2023) and some researchers advocate for “gender budgeting”, which recognizes financial decision-making as a non-neutral political instrument, that has gendered implications and consequences (Steinþórsdóttir et al., 2020).

However, despite the volume of existing research, the global picture remains elusive. Although it is generally accepted that there are gender differences in funding, it is not so clear the extent to which they do. As Cruz-Castro et al. (2022) note in their literature review on the topic, this may be due to the lack of comparative benchmarks between national systems or simply the unavailability of standardized data. A representative example of the lack of consensus in the literature is that of Bornmann et al. (2007) and Marsh et al. (2009). Using the same data, the former research found that men have a 7% higher probability of grant approval than women, while the latter found no significant gender differences (González-Salmón et al., 2025).

Another factor that may provoke divergences in the results are the disciplinary differences, as quantitative research, which is done disproportionately by men, is thought to be more rigorous and thus receives more funding (Larregue and Nielsen, 2024). In the same line, women are usually more present in Social Sciences and Humanities, which includes fields where receiving funding is less common than in STEM (Cidlinská, 2019). This is also true at the European level, where Social Sciences and Humanities research receives residual funding, as stated by Schögler and König (2017).

Given the methodological difficulties, studies on research funding are often conducted at the national level, where it is more likely to access normalized and comparable data. Such analyses reveal, for instance, that men outperform women in securing research funding in Italy (e.g., Bellotti et al., 2022), that women over 38 years old perform worse than men in Quebec (Larivière et al., 2011) and that women Principal Investigators are evaluated less favourably in Canada (Witteman et al., 2019). Furthermore, in the Netherlands, 4% of women are lost during grant review (van der Lee and Ellemers, 2015), although recent changes in the policies of the Talent Programme of the Dutch Research Council have led to a gender gap in the other direction: now men are less likely to be awarded a grant (Albers et al., 2024). A study of the Danish context shows the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to an increase of gender differences in funding, due to a concentration of funding in senior researchers (Madsen et al., 2025). The closest to a global analysis would be research into European funding calls, which represent a supranational experience of funding. In this sense, it has been found that projects with women PI receive lower evaluations (Foss and Olsen, 2024) or that countries with more ERC grant applications show gender differences favouring men (Menichini and Miccoli, 2025).

Gender and Open Access

In recent years, there has been a significant shift toward OA practices in science, especially following the launch of the OA Initiative in 2002 (Budapest Open Access Initiative, 2002). Researchers have explored the pace and extent of adoption of these practices across countries (e.g., Zhu, 2020) and disciplines (e.g., Wallach et al., 2018), and mainly found that the adoption of the practices varies widely but shows a general upward trend (Larivière and Sugimoto, 2018). OA is often associated with increased visibility and equitable dissemination, yet its implementation has also introduced new challenges. Some scholars, such as Zhang et al. (2022), have emphasized that its current implementation often involves rising Article Processing Charges (APCs), which can limit access for researchers in low-resource countries (Klebel and Ross-Hellauer, 2023) or those unaffiliated with well-funded institutions (Burchardt, 2014). Therefore, having lower funding may lead to a lower adoption of Open Access practices, and vice versa (Morillo, 2020), making it necessary to study funding and Open Access practices in tandem.

Evidence on the gender implications of OA remains fragmented. Wilson et al. (2022) examined universities in Australia and the United Kingdom and concluded that OA practices can enhance the visibility of women's work. At the same time, Ayeni and Larivière (2025) analyzed the Canadian case in Social Sciences and Humanities and found five barriers for publishing in OA, one of them being gender. Zhu (2017) analysed a survey across twelve Russell Group universities (United Kingdom) and found that while most researchers support OA principles, women reported lower rates of OA publishing. In Vietnam, Vuong et al. (2021) observed a negative association between women authorship and OA publishing. In the United States, Olejniczak and Wilson (2020) reported a similar trend: across most fields, men researchers exhibit higher rates of OA publishing than their women counterparts, especially in APCs-based models.

Although the aforementioned literature is performed at the national level and each national context has its own characteristics, there is one macro-level image that can be drawn from all the research on gender and OA practices: women tend to publish in OA less than men. This may as well be related to the fact that OA practices are connected to funding availability, and women researchers tend to get less funding (See section 'Gender and funding'). Moreover, it could also be related to the fact that men are invited twice as many times as women to submit papers in journals (Holman et al., 2018), therefore women tend to have less easiness to publish in general, which includes OA journals as well.

In the Spanish context, OA practices have been increasingly shaped by national and European policy mandates. Since 2011, the Ley de la Ciencia, la Tecnología y la Innovación (BOE-A-2011-9617 Ley 14/2011, de 1 de Junio, de La Ciencia, La Tecnología y La Innovación 2011) requires that publicly funded research results be made openly accessible. This mandate was reinforced by the Agencia Estatal de Investigación (AEI), which explicitly demands that publications resulting from funded projects be deposited in open repositories or published in Open Access journals (Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, 2021). Additionally, Spain participates in several national transformative agreements (e.g., CRUE-CSIC with major publishers), which allow affiliated authors to publish in Open Access without incurring APCs directly.

However, these transformative agreements and the implementation of OA in Spain vary in coverage by institution and discipline, as Bordons et al. (2023) show in their analysis of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) publications. In Biology and Biomedicine and Materials Science,

funded publications are far more likely to appear in OA than unfunded ones, while in Humanities and Social Sciences the difference is minimal. Moreover, internationally funded articles have higher OA rates than nationally funded research, particularly via gold and hybrid models. A notable share of unfunded articles published in APC-based journals suggests the influence of institutional support schemes. Thus, the ability to publish in OA is shaped not only by direct project funding, but also by institutional infrastructure and disciplinary norms. These factors have potential implications for equity and visibility. Yet, little is known about whether these OA policies operate differently across gender or authorship positions and, to our knowledge, no prior study has examined this intersection in the Spanish context.

Gender and authorship positions

Although with its caveats, the most straightforward and accepted method in the literature for measuring relevant roles within scientific teams is examining authorship position. There is a vast amount of literature that studies the gender disposition on authorship positions (e.g. Morillo et al., 2025; West et al., 2013; Ni et al., 2021; Son & Bell, 2022; Bunker Whittington et al., 2024; Ross et al., 2022). It is generally accepted that first and last authors contribute more to a publication (Sauermaann and Haeussler, 2017), although this varies by discipline and follows different norms and work culture (Ding et al., 2021; Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2025). Representation of women as first authors varies greatly by field, in some cases literature has found overrepresentation (as in Neuroscience, Neurology, or Psychiatry in Marescotti et al., 2022) and in others underrepresentation (such as in Entomology in Walker 2020). Contrarily, there is strong and uncontested evidence of underrepresentation of women as last authors in most fields (González-Salmón et al., 2025). Interestingly, it has been found a relationship between having women as last authors and the presence of more women in the byline (e.g. Salerno et al., 2019).

Another relevant authorship position is that of corresponding author. Literature has studied this position and found that there is a relationship between being the corresponding author of a publication and being the author who has secured the funding (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019). Researchers are still unsure about the relationship between corresponding authors and seniority, but in some cases being corresponding author is more related to seniority than responsibility (Willems and Plume, 2021). González-Alcaide and Gorráiz (2018) analyzed the area of Information and Library Science in Spain and found a relationship between “leadership” and corresponding author. Research on gender and corresponding authorship shows that women first authors are less likely to be corresponding authors (Fox et al., 2018), that women corresponding authors tend to work with teams containing more women in Cardiovascular Medicine Journals (Ouyang et al., 2019), and that the COVID-19 pandemic disproportionately increased submissions with men as corresponding authors (Bell and Fong, 2021).

Thus, the literature presents a picture in which women remain underrepresented as last authors across most disciplines, while their presence in first authorship positions appears to be increasing. This pattern may be associated with the fact that last authorship is commonly linked to senior academic positions, which have historically been disproportionately occupied by men, due to the so-called “leaky pipeline” (Greska, 2023). Regarding corresponding authorship, gender dynamics remain insufficiently clarified. This study also seeks to contribute to this issue, given that key authorship positions in publications are closely connected to funding opportunities and career advancement, both of which are deeply embedded in gendered structures and relations.

Gender, funding, Open Access and authorship positions

Funding availability differs by gender and disciplines. Precisely, access to research funding may influence the ability to publish in OA venues, particularly in models that require the payment of article processing charges (APCs). At the same time, authorship positions such as first or corresponding authors often play an important role in research evaluation and recognition, which in turn may affect future funding opportunities. Thus, these mechanisms interact and can either reinforce or mitigate structural disadvantages within academic systems. These interconnections suggest that gender differences in funding, authorship roles and Open Access practices should not be analysed in isolation, but as mutually reinforcing dimensions of the scientific reward system. However, research that studies this tripartite relationship remains scarce.

To our knowledge, Ruggieri et al. (2021) provide one of the few analyses integrating these dimensions in Italy (2016–2018), demonstrating that women are more disposed to publish OA and that disciplinary context matters. Nazim et al. (2025) also examine gender, funding, OA, and authorship roles together, finding gender differences, although the small sample size limits generalisation. Building on these studies and the previous literature that analyzes each concept separately, our study aims to advance this agenda by offering new insights into the complex relationship between gender, funding, and OA publishing in the Spanish scientific system.

Material and methods

To conduct the research, data were retrieved from the in-house Web of Science database maintained by the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS, Leiden University) for the period 2008-2017. This version of the WoS includes validated and harmonised metadata on publication year, funding characteristics, Open Access status and types, author gender and author country. The dataset was obtained as a pre-processed bibliometric dataset from CWTS, where standard procedures for data cleaning, metadata standardization and author disambiguation are applied. The selected timeframe is the most recent period for which complete coverage of publications and citations was available at the time of compilation.

The units of analysis are authors and publications. We include all publications with at least one Spanish author, resulting in 473,218 publications, with 893,486 unique authors and 4,437,729 authorships (Figure 1). The methodology used by CWTS for author identification was developed by Caron and van Eck (2014). Gender assignment was conducted by CWTS following the methodology described in Boekhout, van der Weijden and Waltman (2021), which relies on Gender API, Gender Guesser and Genderize.io. Gender was successfully assigned to 75.95% of the authors. After removing authors whose gender could not be assigned (24.05%), the final dataset contains 470,073 publications, that is, 470,073 publications in which the gender of at least one author was assigned. Thus, the final dataset contains 678,587 unique authors, of which 39.08% are women and 60.92% are men. That comprises 2,986,078 authorships. It is important to take into account that 55.58% (377,156) of authors have only one authorship, and 14.84% (100,684) have two. Figure 1 shows the amount of data before and after the gender assignment process.

Figure 1. Data workflow that shows the number of publications, unique authors and authorships before and after the gender assignment process.

To study gender differences in teams, we classify research teams into three different categories: those formed exclusively by women (W), teams formed by men only (M) and mixed-gender teams (Mixed), where both men and women collaborate. W and M categories include single-authorship publications, meaning that publications authored by a single woman or a single man are classified as women-only or men-only teams, respectively. In total, there are 8,800 single-authored publications (1.87% of the total sample), of which 2,424 are single-authorship by women, and 6,456 by men. Visualizations include these categories (W, M and Mixed) individually and jointly with an aggregated field-level indicator (labelled “Total” in the figures) to preserve contextual comparability across domains. This “Total” category represents the overall distribution of publications across all team types within each field. Publications were assigned to one of five broad scientific fields based on the CWTS classification: Biomedical and Health Sciences, Life and Earth Sciences, Mathematics and Computer Science, Physical Sciences and Engineering, and Social Sciences and Humanities. When counting authors by field, we count an author as many times as fields they appear on. In addition, we analyse three key authorship positions: first author, last author, and corresponding author, all available in the CWTS dataset.

Funding information was also retrieved from WoS funding acknowledgments, which have been increasingly available since 2008. While funding metadata is not fully standardized across publications (Álvarez-Bornstein and Montesi, 2020), this variable provides valuable insights into resource allocation and support structures. We categorized funding acknowledgments into four types: a) *Both*: The publication acknowledges both national and international funding sources; b) *International*: Only international funding is mentioned; c) *National*: Only national funding is mentioned, and d) *No data*: No funding information is available for the publication. These categories are based on dichotomous variables included in the CWTS dataset indicating whether national or international funding was acknowledged (coded as 1 or 0).

Open Access status was determined based on whether a publication is openly available or not (OA or not-OA), and further disaggregated into four OA types: Gold, Green, Bronze, and Hybrid. Each type of OA means the following (van Leeuwen et al., 2019):

- Gold: articles published in fully Open Access journals.
- Green: articles made available through open repositories.

- Bronze: articles that publishers do not formally label as Open Access, but that are nevertheless freely accessible in practice.
- Hybrid: articles in subscription-based journals that are made Open Access after the author or authors pay an Open Access fee.

We choose to include OA types in the study since funding and Open Access are closely connected, and differences in publication costs across OA routes may influence the types of Open Access chosen by men and women, thereby contributing to potential gender inequalities in publishing practices.

We calculate a Productivity Index (PI) by dividing the number of publications by the number of unique authors. This approach is conceptually related to common bibliometric definitions of research productivity (Abramo & D'Angelo, 2014). Our PI was inspired by other productivity measures such as the Research Productivity Index done by Halaweh (2020) to calculate the productivity of universities. Taking that into account, we believe it is an informative metric and it was computed for: a) all publications, b) all-men teams, c) all-women teams, d) men in mixed teams, and e) women in mixed teams. In the calculation of the PI, we use full counting regardless of the number of co-authors. Different counting methods have been discussed in the literature to attribute credit in co-authored publications, including full and fractional counting approaches (Gauffriau, 2017).

We also calculate a Women Index (WI), defined as the average proportion of women per publication (number of women authors divided by number of total authors in such papers). Following Ruggieri et al. (2021), we computed WI across scientific fields, funding categories, and OA types.

All analysis and visualizations were conducted in R, using a combination of data aggregation and descriptive statistical techniques such as frequency distributions, relative shares, cross-tabulations, and temporal trend plotting. Whenever possible, figures maintain consistent dimensions to facilitate comparison across sections and to ensure transparency in the interpretation of gender, authorship, funding, and OA patterns. For clarity, most figures present percentages, whereas absolute values are reported in Appendix 1. An interactive dashboard providing access to all figures is available (link: <https://responsiblemetrics.es/triangle-of-inequalities-gender-research-funding-and-open-access-in-spain/>).

Results

General overview of authors and publications

First, we provide an overview of the dataset, both in terms of author and publication level. Figure 2 shows that during the 2008–2017 period men constituted 60.92% (413,373) of all unique authors, while women represented 39.08% (265,214). If we analyze gender presence by field (counting every author as many times as fields they have published on), we can see that although men are the majority in every field, the gender gap varies substantially across disciplines. Women's representation is highest in Biomedical and Health Sciences (44.95%) and Social Sciences and Humanities (42.46%), while the gap widens in Life and Earth Sciences (39.1%) and is most pronounced in Physical Sciences and Engineering (27.74%) and Mathematics and Computer Science (19%). These patterns illustrate the well-known horizontal segregation across scientific domains (Huang et al., 2020).

Figure 2. Overall gender distribution and gender distribution by fields. The pie chart shows unique authors, while in the histogram every unique author appears as many times as fields they have published on.

Figure 3 allows us to see how publications are distributed within fields and other characteristics. Thus, we now show an analysis at the publication level. Firstly, it is important to note that each publication belongs to only one field. The Spanish output (470,073 publications) is concentrated in biomedical fields (33.75%), Physical Sciences and Engineering (28.39%), and Life and Earth Sciences (20.32%). Mathematics and Computer Science (8.92%) and Social Sciences and Humanities (8.62%) account for smaller proportions of the total. Single-author publications (8,880 in total) occur predominantly in Social Sciences and Humanities (51.93%), with a gender distribution skewed towards men authors (62.55%). In contrast, there are considerably fewer single-author publications in the remaining fields, and all present a pronounced gender imbalance in favour of men: 90.81% of single-author publications done by men in Physical Sciences and Engineering, 87.88% in Mathematics and Computer Science, 77.30% in Life and Earth Sciences and 77.00% in Biomedical and Health Sciences. Thus, single authorships show a relatively more balanced gender distribution in Social Sciences and Humanities, but are considerably more skewed towards men in the remaining fields. In this sense, single authorships mirror the gender distribution of W, M and mixed teams in Social Sciences and Humanities, but are considerably more skewed towards men in the remaining fields. When interpreting these results, it is important to take into account that the sample comprises just 8,800 publications.

The vast majority of publications (419,178 articles, or 89.18%) have a single corresponding author, specially in Biomedical and Health Sciences (34.49%), followed by Physical Sciences and

Engineering and Life and Earth Sciences. There are 186 articles (0.04%) with more than one corresponding author. For the purposes of the analysis of corresponding authorship, we will count a paper as many times as corresponding authors it has. About 23% of all publications identify the corresponding author as also being the last author. Again, this is led by Biomedical and Health Sciences (46.51%).

Open Access publications account for 192,045 items, roughly 40% of the total, with a distribution that mirrors the overall field composition: Biomedical and Health Sciences and Physical Sciences and Engineering again dominate. Finally, funding data reveal higher volumes of national funding (167,790 publications), especially in Physical Sciences and Engineering and Biomedical and Health Sciences, while international funding (38,405 publications) is more concentrated in Physical Sciences and Engineering (39.43%) and Life and Earth Sciences (21.03%).

Figure 3. Characteristics of publications by category. Each percentage has been calculated based on the total for each category (there is no overlap between fields).

Scientific production and team composition

After understanding the Spanish publication landscape and the differences in gender distribution across fields, we go into further detail to study the teams that are behind the Spanish scientific production. Figure 4 presents the distribution of publications by authorship type (women-only, men-only, and mixed-gender teams) across fields. Mixed teams are the dominant collaboration mode in most fields and account for most of the Spanish scientific output. Women-only teams consistently produced the smallest share of publications, while men-only teams showed predominance in Mathematics and Computer Science, aligning with the strong masculinization of this field observed in Figure 2.

When comparing these patterns with the distribution of single-author publications described above (Figure 3), similar gender imbalances can be observed. Single-author publications show

patterns that are consistent with those of single-gender teams, particularly the predominance of men in most fields. In contrast, mixed-gender teams display a more balanced gender distribution. These results highlight how gender disparities vary depending on the mode of collaboration.

Figure 4. Percentage of publications by team composition and field. Single-author publications (8,800 publications) are included and classified within the women-only or men-only categories accordingly. The Total category represents the overall distribution of publications across fields within the total number of publications.

When looking at the temporal dimension (Figure 5) and considering the gender distribution in each thematic field, we can observe different disciplinary practices. In all fields, the percentage of women-only publications is lower than that written by men-only teams, throughout the entire period, with the sharpest disparities in Mathematics and Computer Science and Physical Sciences and Engineering. A moderate increase in publications written by only women teams is observed in Social Sciences and Humanities, where men-only publications tend to decrease over time. Mixed teams remain the prevailing form of collaboration across nearly all fields, except in Mathematics and Computer Science, where men-only teams remain dominant. It is important to note that single authorships are included in the analysis.

Figure 5. Evolution of authorship of publications by field and team composition. Single-author publications are included.

Researchers and gender evolution across fields

When the active workforce behind these results (researchers who publish) is taken into account (Figure 6), the distribution of researchers largely mirrors the distribution of publications. Here an author appears once for every field they have published in. We can see that Biomedical and Health Sciences concentrate the largest number of researchers. Gender imbalances echo the patterns already described: women are scarcest in Mathematics and Computer Science and Physical Sciences and Engineering, and better represented in Biomedical and Health Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities.

Figure 6. Percentage of authors by field (an author appears once for every field they have published in). Additionally, it shows the percentage of authors from each field in relation to the total.

Figure 7 shows the temporal evolution of author gender by field. Here authors are counted for every publication in which they appear, using the corresponding year of publication in the analysis. The gender gap remains stable across the decade in STEM fields, especially in Physical Sciences and Engineering and Mathematics and Computer Science, where men consistently represent a clear majority. Biomedical and Health Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities present more balanced gender distribution, while Life and Earth Sciences maintains a relatively stable 35% share of women authors. Disparities seem to only be slowly decreasing in Biomedical and Health Sciences and in Social Sciences and Humanities.

Figure 7. Evolution of authors by publication year and field (percentage).

Funding patterns by gender and authorship roles

As stated in the first research question, we aim at understanding how funding and OA practices are distributed across genders and disciplines. Thus, we now investigate the funding information by disciplines and gender team composition. As we can see in Figure 8, the largest proportion of publications do not have funding data or do not report information on funding. This lack of funding information is a pattern especially pronounced in Social Sciences and Humanities and in women-only teams. When it is acknowledged, funding that comes from both national and international sources is the most frequent category. It is generally observed that 20% of the publications are financed with both types of funds, generally obtained by mixed teams. The next most common situation involves exclusively national funding, followed by exclusively international funding. Mathematics and Computer Science constitutes an exception, as national and international funding account for roughly the same amount.

Figure 8. Type of funding by team composition and field.

When examining differences by team composition, this overall pattern remains, although it is considerably more pronounced in women-only teams (Appendix 1, Figure 7). When funding is reported, women-only teams most frequently acknowledge national funding, with much lower representation in the “Both” and “International” categories. In contrast, men-only teams show consistently higher funding rates across all categories, particularly for combined national and international funding, followed by national and then international funding. This suggests more limited access of women-only teams to diversified funding sources, consistent with previously documented inequalities (Álvarez-Bornstein and Montesi, 2020).

Figure 9 provides a finer-grained view by focusing exclusively on mixed-gender teams and distinguishing funding outcomes depending on which gender occupies the corresponding, first, or last authorship positions by field. In this sense, it helps in answering the second research question, which focuses on the roles of women within research teams and its relation to funding and OA. In Biomedical and Health Sciences the dominant scenario across all author positions is the absence of funding information. However, focusing only on cases where funding is reported, a consistent pattern emerges: when women are corresponding or last authors, mixed-gender teams receive less funding than when men occupy those positions. For first authors, the pattern reverses: mixed teams with women first authors secure more funding than those with men in the same role. Most funded publications fall under national or national and international funding, while international-only funding is rare. In Life and Earth Sciences the picture is different, as the percentage without funding information is lower. Interestingly though, we also see that funding goes mostly to mixed teams where corresponding or last authors are men, and when first authors are women. This parallelism suggests stable authorship-funding dynamics across both life-science domains.

Mathematics and Computer Science and Physical Sciences and Engineering present similar patterns and some of the stronger gender asymmetries. In almost all author positions, mixed teams obtain more funding when relevant positions are held by men. This difference increases substantially for the “Both” (national and international) category, which represents the highest-resourced projects. The only exception is found in Physical Sciences and Engineering for nationally funded publications with women first authors, where women outperform men by a short difference. Beyond this exception, the hierarchy remains consistent: men-led positions within mixed teams correspond to higher levels of funding. Lastly, Social Sciences and Humanities stands out for an overwhelming lack of funding data. However, in the few cases where data are available men dominate funding receipts across corresponding, first, and last author positions. The only exception is national funding for publications with women first authors, echoing the pattern observed in STEM fields whereby women secure more resources as first authors.

Taken together, Figures 8 and 9 reveal a consistent cross-field pattern: First authorship is the only position where women in mixed teams tend to receive more funding, whereas senior positions (corresponding, last author) show systematically higher funding levels when held by men, particularly in resource-intensive and internationalized fields. This suggests that funding distribution is not neutral: it varies by gender, field, and authorship hierarchy.

Figure 9. Percentage of publications by gender, relevant author position and field.

Funding, corresponding authorship and Open Access

The first research question aimed at investigating OA practices across genders and disciplines, and the second to understand the role of women within teams. Therefore, we now look at the relationship between Open Access publication and gender distribution across one particular

relevant position: corresponding author (Figure 10). In all team configurations (women-only, men-only, mixed teams with women corresponding authors, and mixed teams with men corresponding authors) the most frequent scenario is the absence of funding information, consistent with earlier figures. This pattern is especially pronounced for women-only authorship.

Despite this limitation, several relevant patterns emerge: Publications with combined national and international funding (“Both”) show the highest proportion of Open Access, regardless of whether the corresponding author is a man or a woman. However, all-women teams do not follow this pattern: for them, OA is not clearly associated with the “Both” category but with national funding. For the remaining teams, nationally funded and internationally funded publications typically show lower OA proportions, suggesting that mixed or diversified funding facilitates OA compliance and homogeneous funding may not.

Figure 10. Type of funding by type of authorship and open access. Labels are shown for values above 4% to improve readability.

To contextualize the results, Figure 11 shows the evolution of OA publications over time. OA rose from roughly 30% in 2008 to nearly 50% in 2017. That means that nowadays, after more than one decade of OA policies, half of the research produced in Spain comply with OA requirements. This reveals uneven uptake and partial compliance across fields and funding contexts, which is consistent with global trends (Larivière and Sugimoto 2018). Overall, Figures 10 and 11 indicate that the adoption of OA is largely shaped by funding availability and disciplinary practices.

Figure 11. Total publication count (grey), total Open Access publication count (green) and percentage of Open Access publication (orange).

Productivity Index

Next, we contextualize the results by adding a Productivity Index (PI) to the analysis, which allows us to understand different publication and research practices across genders. The PI (Table 1) shows that on average, every researcher contributes to slightly more than half an article over the analyzed period (0.53). This number could reflect division of labour amongst collaboration networks. Comparison amongst gender shows a gap in the productivity between men and women when they work in no gender-mixed teams. All-men teams have an average productivity which is four times higher than that of all-women teams (0.32 vs 0.08). This result is consistent with previous studies that associate lower productivity in women, known as the *productivity puzzle* (e.g., Cole and Zuckerman, 1984, Campbell and Simberloff, 2022, Huang et al., 2020).

When looking at mixed teams, the results show a different pattern. Women’s productivity (1.25) in these teams exceeds that of men (0.93). This suggests that collaboration in mixed environments can encourage women’s active participation and contribution. This result could be understood as an effect of equal participation: when women have access to broader and more collaborative networks, their production levels approach or even exceed those of their men colleagues. This result is consistent with studies on the importance of collaboration in reducing productivity gaps regardless of the source of information used (i.e. Elsevier, 2020, which used Scopus data).

Table 1. Productivity Index for all men teams, all women teams, men in mixed teams and women in mixed teams.

Type	Calculation	Productivity Index
Total	Total number of publications / total number of authors	0.53

All-men	Total number publications All-men / total number of men	0.32
All-women	Total number publications All-women / total number of women	0.08
Men in mixed teams	Total number of publications mixed / number of men in mixed	0.93
Women in mixed teams	Total number of publications mixed / number of women in mixed	1.25

Women Index

Lastly, we use the Women Index (WI) as a way of merging all variables together, and understanding how the intersection of field, funding, OA and OA types is interconnected to the notion of gender. Following Ruggieri et al. 2021, Figure 12 shows the WI for all publications and by field, funding, OA status and OA types (detailed in Table A2.1 in Appendix 2). Red bars indicate the total number of publications and yellow bars represent those done only by mixed teams. We can also see the average for each group of publications. The global WI shows that an average of a third of authors per publications are women (0.33). The WI goes up (0.42) when taking into account only mixed teams.

We have analyzed this data by field and we can see a persistent underrepresentation of women authors. The highest values are recorded in Biomedical and Health Sciences (0.40) and Social Sciences and Humanities (0.38), followed by Life and Earth Sciences (0.37). In contrast, Physical Sciences and Engineering (0.25) and especially Mathematics and Computer Science (0.17) show a pronounced low WI. These disciplinary differences reflect historical patterns of horizontal segregation in science (Huang et al. 2020), by which women are more represented in Social and Biomedical Sciences than they are in STEM areas (Lawson et al., 2021; González-Salmón et al., 2025).

Interestingly, mixed teams systematically show a higher WI compared to all publications, especially for Mathematics and Computer Science. This difference is lower in Biological and Health Sciences. This fact reinforces the idea that collaborative contexts and inclusive scientific cultures contribute to improving the productivity and visibility of women researchers (Elsevier, 2020).

Figure 12. Women Index (average proportion of women per paper) by discipline, funding, and open-access type.

Analysis by funding type shows that nationally funded teams have the highest WI (0.36), followed by unfunded teams (0.33). In contrast, the WI is lower when funding is only international (0.30) and for mixed funding (0.31). As earlier, when only considering mixed teams, the WI increases. This pattern is consistent with previous studies that indicate that women are more dependent on national funding (Ruggieri et al., 2021) and that international collaboration and projects tend to be dominated by men (Kwiek and Roszka, 2021). In contrast, national programs seem to maintain a somewhat more balanced gender distribution, suggesting a greater compensatory effect. In this sense, national policies may play a compensatory role in gender equity, while internationalization, despite being associated with greater impact and visibility, may reproduce preexisting inequalities

Differences between OA and not-OA publications are modest: Women Index is slightly lower in OA publications (0.32) than in closed access publications (0.34). Differences in mixed teams are again modest (from 0.41 for OA and 0.43 for non-OA). When broken down by type, the highest values are recorded in gold OA (0.36) and bronze OA (0.34), followed by green OA (0.31) and hybrid OA (0.30). In mixed teams the highest WI is found in Gold OA (0.43), followed by Green and Bronze (both with a WI of 0.40) and Hybrid (0.39). However, these differences continue to be relatively small.

The regression models presented in table A2.2 (Appendix 2) allow us to identify the factors that significantly influence the Women Index (WI). We estimated linear regression models to analyse the proportion of women in mixed teams as a function of field and funding category. Although all parameters appear highly significant, the coefficient of determination is low, indicating that the results should be interpreted with caution.

We use Biomedical and Health Sciences as the reference category, as gender parity is close to being achieved in this field, and it is the predominant field in our dataset. By doing so, the estimates indicate that shifting to Life and Earth Sciences is associated with a 1.15% decrease in the share of women; shifting to Mathematics and Computer Science corresponds to a 6.29% decrease; and shifting to Physical Sciences and Engineering implies a 7.11% decrease. In contrast, moving to Social Sciences and Humanities is associated with a 2.19% increase of the WI.

Now we use no funding acknowledged as the reference funding category as it represents the least institutionally mediated research context. It can be interpreted as a neutral baseline against which the gendered effects of different funding configurations are assessed. Taking no funding acknowledged as the reference, the model suggests that mixed national–international funding is associated with a 1.08% decrease in the share of women, exclusively international funding with a 0.77% decrease, and exclusively national funding with a 2.73% increase. This is in line with previous results.

Discussion

The analysis confirms that gender inequalities in Spanish science persist, although they manifest differently depending on discipline, type of funding, authorship position, and publishing practices. Women represent slightly under 40% of the total workforce publishing in journals indexed in the Web of Science database for the period 2008-2017. Their participation is mainly concentrated in Biomedical and Health Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities, while it is much lower in Mathematics and Computer Science and Physics and Engineering. This uneven distribution mirrors

well-established patterns of horizontal segregation reported in the literature (Huang et al., 2020), in which women have increased their participation but remain structurally underrepresented in STEM fields.

Differences in access to funding are particularly relevant to consider, since funding bodies influence both the type of knowledge that is produced and the conditions under which such knowledge is evaluated and rewarded (Álvarez-Bornstein and Montesi, 2020). Regarding the first research question (How are research funding and OA practices distributed across genders and disciplines?), we find that most funded work comes from national calls for proposals, reflecting the structure of the Spanish R&D system and the policy of the State Research Agency (AEI). However, men-only teams account for a disproportionately large share of funded publications, especially for publications supported simultaneously by national and international sources. In contrast, women-only teams show much lower funding rates, and their presence is mainly limited to nationally funded projects rather than international or mixed funding sources. These findings align with previous research documenting the overrepresentation of men in international funding schemes and persistent gender biases in competitive evaluation processes (Bellotti et al., 2022; Cruz-Castro et al., 2022). They also align with findings in Italy by Ruggieri et al. (2021), where women also accessed more national funding. This may reflect structural similarities between the highly centralised scientific systems of Italy and Spain. Besides, Díaz-Faes et al. (2025) showed that teams with access to a more diverse range of funding show higher interdisciplinarity. This raises the question whether all-men teams have more options for interdisciplinarity since they account for more dual funding. However, this logic can also be reversed: it may be possible that more interdisciplinary teams, due to their nature, have greater access to diversified funding sources.

Recent evidence also suggests that the standardisation and traceability of funding information remains incomplete, particularly when distinguishing national and European programmes, which may render part of women's output less visible (Bordons et al., 2024) and affect the visibility of funding agencies. This shortcoming could partly explain the volume of lack of standardisation in our study, especially in the Social Sciences and Humanities. Although Spanish legislation mandates the acknowledgement of funding sources, established by Science Law 14/2011, efforts to assess whether funding inequalities are wider than the available data suggest are needed. In this sense, it is remarkable the work done to better understand funding acknowledgements, such as Perianes-Rodríguez et al. (2024).

When adding authorship positions to the analysis, we can answer the second research question (What are the roles do women occupy within research teams, and how are these roles associated with funding patterns and OA publishing?). Here the results show that internal team hierarchies also reproduce gender inequalities. Across mixed-gender teams, men disproportionately occupy last and corresponding author positions traditionally associated with greater seniority and responsibility in publication (González-Alcaide and Gorráiz, 2018). Women appear more frequently as first authors, a position more closely associated with the operational and execution components of research responsible for the direct execution of the work. The results show that, when men hold last or corresponding authorship positions, publications are more likely to report funding; conversely, when women are first authors, they tend to receive more funding than their men counterparts. However, this pattern does not extend in STEM fields, where gender imbalances in the research workforce are stronger.

The interplay between funding and OA introduces an additional complexity. Despite long-standing national and European OA mandates (BOE-A-2011-9617 Ley 14/2011, de 1 de Junio, de La Ciencia, La Tecnología y La Innovación 2011), only about half of the Spanish publications analysed are OA at the end of the period. This partial compliance is consistent with the findings of Larivière and Sugimoto (2018) and Bordons et al. (2023), which show steady but uneven progress across disciplines and institutions. The results show that publications funded by combined funding sources have the highest OA rates, suggesting that diversified resources facilitate compliance with OA mandates. However, the adoption of OA does not appear to be strongly associated with greater gender equity, indicating that openness patterns reflect broader structural dynamics.

Productivity indicators reinforce these conclusions. In non-mixed teams, men's productivity exceeds that of women, in line with well-documented inequalities in access to resources and networks (Lawson et al., 2021). In mixed teams, productivity levels converge and even reverse, with women showing slightly higher productivity than men. This suggests that collaborative environments can mitigate productivity gaps, although they do not fully eliminate them.

The Women Index (WI) analysis across fields, funding types, OA implementation, and OA categories reveals a persistent gender underrepresentation of women across all dimensions. Mixed teams consistently achieve higher WI values across all areas, particularly in Mathematics and Computer Science, supporting the idea that collaborative and inclusive environments enhance women's participation and visibility in research. In terms of funding, nationally funded publications show the highest WI (0.37), whereas international and combined funding categories show lower values (0.30–0.31), consistent with the literature that indicates men's dominance in international funding circuits (Kwiek and Roszka, 2021; Ruggieri et al., 2021). This pattern again suggests that national funds may provide more equitable opportunities, whereas international funding tends to reproduce gendered access barriers. Finally, differences in WI between open and closed access publications are moderate: open access outputs exhibit slightly lower average values (0.32 vs. 0.34). Within OA models, gold and bronze routes show a slightly higher WI than green and hybrid, implying that fully open models may foster somewhat greater inclusion.

When the main variables examined in this work (funding, team composition, authorship roles, and Open Access) are considered together, the overall picture suggests that women are formally permitted to participate in the scientific system under the same rules as men. In practice, however, they appear to be situated within a vicious circle characterized by horizontal segregation into fields that receive lower levels of funding, such as the Social Sciences and Humanities. Moreover, when women do obtain funding, it is more likely to be national rather than international or both (national and international) in origin, and the regression model supports these results. At the same time, it is precisely the presence of a more diverse set of funding sources that is associated with greater Open Access publishing. A similar pattern emerges in relation to relevant positions. When women occupy leading authorship roles, they are less likely to receive funding, except when they are first authors, a position that is generally less associated with seniority than last authorship.

These results highlight the interdependence of structural and collaborative dimensions: team composition, authorship hierarchy, and access to funding jointly shape women's participation and visibility in scientific production. In this sense, the issue is not that women do not produce scientific output. On the contrary, the PI shows that, when women participate in mixed teams, they are more productive than men. This suggests that there are structural factors that prevent an equal playing field

for men and women, and that these inequalities cannot be attributed to women's absence from the system or to a lack of effort on their part.

The causal mechanisms underlying these observed gender disparities may be multiple and interrelated. Although the present research does not seek to establish causal explanations, we understand that the differences identified are linked, at least in part, to a persistent structural sexism within academia. Scientific work is not produced in isolation; rather, it is embedded in social and institutional environments in which sexism behavior still exists (Bevan & Learmonth, 2013). The patterns identified in this work are consistent with broader interpretations of academic inequality as cumulative disadvantages that lead to persistent forms of exclusion and devaluation (Tower & Latimer, 2016; Azoulay & Lynn, 2020). These dynamics have also been discussed in the literature through mechanisms such as cumulative advantage, or the "Matthew effect" in science (Merton, 1968), as well as the progressive loss of women across academic career stages commonly referred to as the "leaky pipeline" (Greska, 2023). Taken together, these findings point to the need for targeted measures aimed at improving both the well-being and the opportunities of women in academia.

Limitations and further research

There are limitations to the research that should be taken into account when interpreting the results. First, the analysis is constrained by the time frame of the dataset, 2008-2017. Although this period captures an important decade in the evolution of Open Access policies and funding practices, it does not reflect more recent transformations. The patterns identified here should therefore be understood as representative of an earlier stage in the evolution of these dynamics. Second, the gender assignment algorithm used in this study follows a binary logic and infers gender from names. This approach, common in large-scale bibliometric studies, simplifies gender identities in a binary way and assumes that gender can be inferred from a first name. As a result, these gender assignments do not capture the full spectrum of gender realities. Thirdly, the dataset contains substantial gaps in funding and OA information. Missing or incomplete metadata may restrict the visibility and openness of publications produced by both men and women. In particular, the high proportion of missing funding information should be taken into account when interpreting the distribution of funding types across team compositions and fields. Excluding publications without funding information would substantially reduce the size of the dataset and alter the interpretation of funding patterns; therefore, these cases are retained in the analysis to reflect the empirical structure of the data.

Regarding future research, incorporating additional variables such as career stage, contributorship information or institutional involvement in transformative agreements could provide more granular insights into how gender intersects with other structural dimensions. Finally, some analysis, particularly those related to national funding procedures, could not be conducted because the necessary data are not publicly available, since the Spanish Ministry does not make the necessary data publicly available, regardless of the 2013 access to public information and good governance law (BOE-A-2013-12887 Ley 19/2013, de 9 de diciembre, de transparencia, acceso a la información pública y buen gobierno, 2013). In line with Álvarez-Bornstein and Montesi (2020), we reiterate that transparency in the distribution of research funding is an essential responsibility of funding agencies and a prerequisite for rigorous and equitable evaluation. Access to such data would enable more comprehensive and methodologically robust analyses in future work.

Implications

Initiatives such as CoARA, national Open Science strategies, and the growing emphasis on responsible metrics have created a window of opportunity in which evidence-based reforms are both needed and explicitly sought. This aligns with findings in the literature suggesting that peer-review processes benefit from decisions grounded in empirical evidence (e.g., Liu et al., 2025). In this context, the findings of this study serve not as prescriptive criteria but as diagnostic tools that can inform reforms aimed at reducing gender inequalities and improving the fairness of evaluation systems. Table 2 summarizes the implications and policy recommendations this research could have in funding policy, research assessment and OA policies.

Table 2. Implications and recommendations of the research by type.

Type	Implication/recommendation
Funding policies	Need to improve the standardisation and completeness of funding acknowledgements. Consider how national schemes may mitigate unequal access to international funding.
Research assessment	Reflect on how heavy reliance on some relevant authorship positions (e.g. last or corresponding author) may disadvantage women Always consider authorship positions in their disciplinary context. Study the recognition of additional forms of leadership, other than authorship.
OA policies	Consider how gender-disaggregated monitoring can help detect who benefits and who is constrained by APC-based models Contemplate integrating OA policies with funding and assessment reforms.

Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of how funding patterns, team structures and Open Access practices intersect with women’s participation in scientific production in Spain. The findings reflect a system where funding allocation, authorship positions and open access practices intersect to reproduce gender inequalities through combined mechanisms. National funding appears to mitigate some gender differences, while women’s presence in first authorship positions emerges as a relevant factor. In contrast, open access practices seem to be influenced by additional variables, and their analysis does not reveal a clear gender pattern.

Overall, the study demonstrates the value of integrated evidence for informing ongoing reforms. By situating gender disparities within the broader configuration of funding, team hierarchy and publication practices, it provides a timely foundation for institutions seeking to implement more inclusive and context-sensitive approaches to research assessment. These findings should be considered when designing funding policies, as increasing funding alone is unlikely to lead to a more equitable scientific system of evaluation mechanisms that systematically favour men who remain unexamined and unchallenged.

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Appendix 1.

This appendix presents relevant graphs used throughout the publication with absolute values shown instead of percentages.

Figure A1.1. Number of publications by authorship gender and field

Figure A1.2. Evolution of publications by authorship gender and field. Note that the scale for the General graph is different.

Figure A1.3. Researchers gender by field

Figure A1.4. Researchers evolution by gender and field. Note that the scale for the General graph is different.

Figure A1.5. Type of funding by authorship gender and field. Note that the scale for the General graph is different.

Figure A1.6. Type of funding by type of authorship and open access, absolute values.

Figure A1.7. Type of funding by type of authorship (only M and W) and open access, percentage.

Appendix 2.

Table A2.1. Women Index (general, by field, type of funding, Open Access, and OA type) for all publications and mixed teams.

Dimensions		Category	WI all		WI mixed teams	
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD
General			0.33	0.28	0.42	0.18
Field	PHY-ENGI		0.25	0.25	0.37	0.18
	BIO-HEALTH		0.40	0.26	0.44	0.19
	MATH-COMP		0.17	0.24	0.38	0.15
	SS-HUM		0.38	0.35	0.47	0.16
	LIFE-EARTH		0.37	0.28	0.43	0.18
Funding	National		0.37	0.28	0.44	0.19
	International		0.30	0.27	0.40	0.18
	Both		0.31	0.26	0.40	0.19
	None		0.33	0.29	0.43	0.18
Open Access	Is OA		0.32	0.27	0.41	0.19
	Is not OA		0.34	0.29	0.43	0.18
OA type	Gold		0.36	0.28	0.43	0.18
	Green		0.31	0.27	0.40	0.18
	Bronze		0.34	0.26	0.40	0.19
	Hybrid		0.30	0.26	0.39	0.18

Table A2.2. Regression analysis of the Women Index on mixed authorship, controlling for research field and funding.

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	Significance
(Intercept)	0.4429892	0.0005685	779.214	< 2e-16	***
Field: LIFE-EARTH	-0.0114810	0.0008537	-13.448	< 2e-16	***
Field: MATH-COMP	-0.0629474	0.0015210	-41.385	< 2e-16	***
Field: PHY-ENGI	-0.0711215	0.0008234	-86.376	< 2e-16	***
Field: SS-HUM	0.0219158	0.0013716	15.979	< 2e-16	***
Funding: Both	-0.0108142	0.0008332	-12.979	< 2e-16	***
Funding: International	-0.0076878	0.0012067	-6.371	1.88e-10	***
Funding: National	0.0272759	0.0009230	29.552	< 2e-16	***

Residual Standard Error: 0.1813 on 317869 degrees of freedom

Multiple R² = 0.03592 | Adjusted R² = 0.03589

F-statistic: 1692 on 7 and 317869 DF | p < 2.2e-16